

Semantic modelling of energy-related information throughout the whole building lifecycle

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ABSTRACT: In the IntUBE project, we proposed an energy-information integration platform to model energy information throughout the whole building life cycle. This “platform” approach, however, limited the energy information to the domains established by the data repositories and constrained the relations between data to their contents. In a later project, RÉPENER, we have overcome these limitations by adopting the Linked Open Data approach to create a semantically-based energy information system. In this paper we present the structure of the system and the results obtained in the first implementation phase.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Context

Energy related information is dispersed in proprietary databases and open data sources; it is heterogeneous, since it is generated by different applications (modelling and simulation programs, monitoring systems); and it is compartmentalised by reference to the various stages of the building lifecycle; from design, to construction, and operation. Because of this, energy information is difficult to acquire at the moment and in the required format, it cannot be properly processed due to problems of interoperability between applications and it cannot be adequately analysed since data sets remain specific to particular stages, e.g. design, operation.

However, to improve the energy efficiency of buildings it is necessary to have a better knowledge of the relationship between design and performance, between the decisions taken at the project level and during building operation and use. This requires, firstly, having access to energy related data throughout the different stages of the whole building lifecycle and, secondly, to process it in such a way that it becomes improved quality information enabling the various stakeholders to take better informed decisions in their respective decision making realms (design, maintenance).

The application of semantic web technologies can help to overcome all of these limitations. In the RÉPENER project, we have applied ontologies to model the energy data from different sources to then create dedicated services to improve the decision making of the different actors involved in the energy performance of buildings.

1.2 Semantic technologies and energy information

Semantic technologies have to date been applied to model energy information in specific domains, mostly those concerning building use and operation. Shah & Chao (2011) have developed an ontology based on electrical home appliances to make consumption visible to households in order to reduce energy consumption. With the same purpose in mind, a smart home knowledge base has been developed using semantic web standards (Kofler et al. 2012). Also, a set of layered ontologies has been used to support a heterogeneous device platform which can recognise devices when connected to a platform (Noguero et al. 2011). Ontology inference processes have been used to enhance a building management system based on ontology modelling (Han et al. 2011). Still, semantic technologies have been applied with the purpose of ensuring interoperability among industry standards for devices, such as BACnet, KNX, LON, or EnOcean (Kabitzsch & Ploennings 2011). Goble and De Roure (2002) proposed bringing smart grid and semantic web together, thus describing grid services through semantics. More recently, the semantic web has been proposed as a foundation for Smart Grid communication architecture (Wagner et al. 2010).

Although we find in the recent literature applications of semantic technologies to specific domains related to energy efficiency in buildings –operation, interoperability, smart grid – there has not to date been as much work done with regard to the model-

2 SEMANTIC ENERGY INFORMATION SYSTEM

In this section we describe the components of the semantic energy information system we are developing in the RÉPENNER project.

2.1 Actors

As described in Figure 1, actors can play different roles interacting with the information system: getting information (*user*), providing sources of information (*source provider*), and providing services (*service provider*). The same actor can play a different role at different stages of the building lifecycle. They obtain data from the system and/or provide new data to the system. For instance, a design team may ask the information system about buildings similar to the one being designed in order to understand the consequences of some design decisions regarding energy performance. Also, the data generated during the design (models, energy simulation inputs and outputs, lists of materials, certifications, etc.) can be integrated into the information system so that it can be used by future actors.

Figure 1. Actor roles.

2.2 Information system

The semantic information system we are developing addresses interoperability issues between different data sources using semantic technologies (Fig. 2). Ontologies are designed using the OWL standard language and data is exposed on the Internet using the RDF language following the Linked Open Data (LOD) initiative. This way the interoperability problem is resolved since all data sources are described by means of a common language, which can be processed by humans and/or machines, using standard protocols. Ontology matching is a powerful semantic technique for interconnecting ontologies making their amalgamation feasible (Euzenat 2011). Once it is done, the conjunction of ontologies and their interconnection facilitate integrated access to heterogeneous energy data by providing: 1. A common vocabulary to unify different areas of knowledge or expertise which are, today, separated, 2. An integrated way to explore energy information and its related data and 3. Compound bulk data on which

data analysis can be performed using data mining techniques. This third feature will retrofit the information system adding new data relations improving the exploration experience.

Figure 2. Information system structure.

2.3 Energy model

At the core of the semantic information system lies an energy model in which data sources are classified and structured in terms, relations, types and units which are common to all of them. The energy model embraces two kinds of energy information (Fig. 3): building information (building systems, consumption, climate), and contextual data (economics, social). For the available data sources, energy parameters are analysed and classified and also relationships between them are identified. Based on this study, an open and flexible data structure is created jointly by energy experts and ontology engineers. As a result of this study of the data sources, an energy model is implemented as a global ontology which is the union of the sets of terms from all data sources. Uschold (2000) states that a global ontology can be the intersection of all local ontologies if it will be used as a shared component of them. On the other hand, a global ontology can be understood as a neutral reference which results from the union of all local ontologies. Local ontologies are then mapped to this neutral reference. In our case, services and tools use the global ontology to retrieve and store data from the system, so the global ontology should contain all terms which can be used in a query.

riched data specified as RDF triple can be very time consuming and inefficient. There are two options for implementing an ontology repository: using a native triple store or applying SPARQL-SQL rewriters in the case where the data is already stored in a relational database. Bizer & Schultz (2009) benchmarked several storage systems including both alternatives, concluding rewriters narrowly outperformed native triple stores. We have opted for the Virtuoso server because the private data sources we are working with are stored in systems not supported by common rewriters. Also, this server delivers a high level of performance in large dataset scenarios.

3 IMPLEMENTATION

In this section we describe the work that has been carried out to date with regard to the implementation of the energy information system outlined in the previous section.

In order to develop the system, we have adopted a case study methodology (Fig. 5). A case defines a scope within which semantically modelled data interacts with dedicated services to provide higher quality information to stakeholders operating at different stages of the building lifecycle.

Figure 5. Case study methodology to reduce complexity.

The proprietary data sources used in the implementation have been provided by Leako, a Basque company dedicated to installation, distribution and HVAC control, which maintains a database of energy consumption data (e.g. thermal consumption for air and water heating, and water consumption) and indoor conditions (e.g. air temperature) for several buildings, and by Icaen, an organisation of the Catalan government which collects the energy certificates of newly planned buildings including their simulated performance. This proprietary data has been combined with other public data sources in order to develop the ontology model.

So far, the results achieved in this research are a set of new interconnected ontologies, for each of the proprietary data sources, which have been connected to other external ontologies. The ontologies have been made available over the Internet in accordance

with the premises of the LOD initiative. Also, we have applied data mining techniques to this data and have created a prototype interface which enables different stakeholder profiles to explore the semantic data.

3.1 Data integration

The first step in creating the set of interconnected ontologies is to integrate the sources of data provided by Leako and Icaen (Fig. 6). An ontology has been designed for each one of these sources based on the data structure of the energy model described in Section 2.3 which contains concepts and relations shared by stakeholders, services and data through the different stages of the building lifecycle. However, not all the contents of these databases were incorporated in the energy model. For this reason, it has been necessary to define new concepts and relations to integrate this data into the ontology since we could not find existing ontologies which could be reused.

Once the ontologies had been designed, the data was transformed to RDF format which is the standard to describe resources on the Internet. The original data has been stored in the source databases. An ETL process has been applied to translate relational databases into RDF. D2RQ (Bizer & Cyganiak 2007) mapping language has been used to obtain RDF dumps which have been uploaded to an RDF server (Virtuoso server). The mappings have been carried out manually by ontology engineers translating each table and column of the database to reflect the correct term and property. The URI pattern selected to identify the instances uses pluralised class names and an identifier. This pattern was selected because it is human readable and easily generated from a database where identifiers are always present (Dodds & Davis 2011).

The last step in the data integration process is to interconnect the data. We have used the SILK tool (Volz et al. 2009) to generate alignments between the data from Leako and Icaen with Linked GeoData (<http://linkedgeo.org/>), which provided spatial data, and Aemet, which provides climate data from the Spanish Meteorological Agency (<http://aemet.linkeddata.es/>). Once these mappings have been carried out, the data can be accessed in an integrated way combining data originating from different sources and domains.

4 CONCLUSIONS

With the RÉPENER project, we have started to develop an information system which models the data generated throughout the building lifecycle using semantic technologies. The work presented in this paper corresponds to the first stage of development of the system. So far, we have been able to provide access to a set of semantically modelled data sources which are highly interconnected. Data mining techniques have been applied to extract information from the semantic data. However, we cannot yet confirm that using semantic techniques to model the data generated throughout the overall building lifecycle can provide higher quality information which in turn helps to improve buildings' energy efficiency. To confirm this, we will need to have access to a larger set of data from more buildings encompassing the various stages of the lifecycle.

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